

Parenting Styles As Perceived By Children And Their Relationship To Behavioral Problems During The Corona Pandemic (Covid 19)

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: December 30, 2020</p> <p>Accepted: March 31, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Parenting Style, Behavioral Problems, Family Relationship</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4651459</p>	<p><i>This study aimed to reveal the impact of parenting styles on children's behavioral problems, especially in childhood during the Corona pandemic. The sample consisted of (300) children: (150) males and (150) females within the age (5-16) years from the city of Irbid. They were chosen randomly by distributing the questionnaires electronically via social media. To achieve the objectives of the study, the researcher used two measures: parenting styles and behavioral problems, following the correlational descriptive approach, and the statistical treatments of the data collected. The results indicated that there is an effect of parenting styles on the behavioral problems of children to a moderate degree, and the presence of an effect of parenting styles on behavioral problems of children due to the different methods of parenting styles and gender. The results also indicated that the most prominent behavioral problem resulting from the parenting styles for both sexes is the problem of lying, and the least prominent is the problem of aggressive behavior.</i></p>

Introduction

A family is the first basic building block in every society in which an individual spontaneously begins to shape his personality and becomes self-aware by his interaction with the members of his family. Society has undoubtedly encouraged the establishment of a family to carry out several responsibilities including the upbringing of children since raising children within the family differs from the nurture provided by a school or in any other institution. Family upbringing is the passkey to considerable success and to attaining a better life for everyone by performing a set of methods stemmed from the nature of each family. The type of parenting style is affected by various factors such as family size, cultural and educational level, and the type of family relationship.

Parenting style is defined as a process of "social interaction between parents and children through which children naturally acquire their social personality, and it reflects the culture of their society. This process is carried out by parents following a set of methods in raising their children and in guiding them how to handle different situations they face, considering parents a source of authority that should be promptly obeyed and a source of knowledge and ideal that should be followed" (Al-Zaliti, 2008). It is also defined as "the specific procedures and methods that parents follow in raising their children socially, and the attitudes they adopt in directing their behavior" (Belaid, 2010).

Based on the previous definitions, it can be said that parenting style is a set of behaviors that parents utilized regularly towards their children in various situations. In this regard, a family is considered the reference framework that defines the behavior of its members, as it shapes their lives and adds natural characteristics to it. It also performs the first socialization process that traditionally relies on social customs, traditions, norms, rules of conduct, and public morals (Al-Sayed et al. 1998).

Given that the individual is a social being by nature, he cannot live in isolation from others, as he is affected by the different situations and experiences he has experienced in his family relationships and these experiences are among the most influential family factors because they play a major role in the upbringing of an individual (Misbah, 2003), these factors include:

First: the type of family relationships

The family environment contributes to the process of socialization through social relationships, family interactions, and the different emotional traits that color these relationships. Generally, family relations vary from one family to another according to the nature of the social and economic status and the composition of the family. Besides, the interaction prevailing among its members. In a matter of fact, when an atmosphere of stability and harmony prevails among family members, the relationship of its members is characterized by love and respect, cooperation, and understanding, unlike the family in which hostility and turmoil prevail among its members. This later affects the personality of the individual, either positively or negatively.

Second: the size of the family.

No one can deny that the size of the family is considered one of the most influential factors that affect social upbringing, especially the practice of parenting style which has been assured by diverse studies. The individual who lives in a nuclear family receives extensive care, for this reason, their parental practice is dominated by excessive protection and indulgence, whereas the individual from the extended family encounters neglect and control over one party without the other. Parents of extended families lack the ability to control their children's behaviors. This leads to the opinion saying that the size of the family is one of the variables that determine the quality of communication between its members and the larger the size of the family, the smaller the role of parents in controlling the behavior of their children.

Third: the economic level of the family.

The economic level is among the factors that contribute to the provision of the material demands of individuals, such as the individual's need for education, various entertainment means, and the nature of the residence. All these matters affect parents' attitudes towards raising their children. Where in a family that suffers from low economic status, permanent conflicts between the parents emerged, which negatively affects their treatment of their children and their ability to utilize the most appropriate educational methods for their proper upbringing.

Fourth: Parents' level of education.

Parents' level of education is a vital element in the upbringing of children, as education is an effective mechanism by which an individual learns different knowledge, through which he acquires the skills that help him to achieve independence, respect, and self-reliance. Some studies have shown that parents who tend to distance themselves from intransigence and corporal punishment in their methods of education, prefer to use discussion and new scientific methods, encourage diligence in learning, and provide children with the opportunity for self-reliance and independence.

Fifth: parenting trends.

Social upbringing differs from one family to another according to the culture of each family. An individual through the first years of his upbringing and social upbringing needs his parents as he spends most of his life with them, especially his early years. Consequently, parents' attitudes determine their children's behavior. In this regard, parents' attitude is defined as the parents' realization of their educational role and the responsibilities and duties entitled to them that later play a vital role in shaping the behavior of their children.

Sixth: Pressures

Parents experience pressures of different kinds such as psychological, financial, social pressures resulting from the environment and surrounding circumstances. Besides, they may be subject to health pressures such as diseases and epidemics, therefore, pressures of different types also have a critical impact on the family system, its relationships, and power centers in it, and these pressures may attribute to raising children or work conditions. Despite this fact, families always strive to adapt to these pressures to achieve the best for their children.

Study and attention to children's behaviors are one of the most critical factors for measuring the progress and development of societies. In fact, caring for the child is a concern for the future of the whole nation (Al-Dahiri, 2008). The issue of behavioral problems among children is of great concern to parents, educators, and researchers, and this concern has been addressed in studies and research on this subject in various fields of education.

Behavioral problems are defined as undesirable behavior that is difficult to confront and represents an incompatible behavior of the individual (Mansour et al., 2002). Some yielded that behavioral problem is "physical, expressive, psychological or social difficulties that face the individual repeatedly, that he can only overcome by resorting to the instructions of his parents and teachers. If these problems remain, they lead to difficulties in the individual's compatibility with others and consequently hinder his psychological and social development resulting in his adoption to a behavior that is socially unacceptable, such as avoiding interaction with others, which weakens his self-confidence, which limits his effectiveness and ability to learn, or even positive participation with others." (Al-Mahadin and Al-Nawais, 2009).

Regarding the behavioral problems children suffer from, they are manifested in rapid emotional changes, impulsivity and compulsion, lack of control and repetition of inappropriate behavior, social withdrawal and introversion, the tendency to laziness and lethargy, distraction and shyness, and the inability to build or maintain interpersonal relationships (Al-Qaryoti et al, 2001), which may lead to feelings of depression, hopelessness, introversion, sadness, and the desire to rebel against sources of authority in the family, school and society (Pryanka, 2013).

Therefore, parenting style is one of the most prominent social factors that play a role in shaping children's healthy and effective personality that contributes efficiently to their society. In addition to the great importance of educating children and helping them to advance in various fields through the prevailing atmosphere within the family and the extent of its effectiveness, this admirably qualifies them for the role they play actively in their community and the surrounding societies. In a matter of fact, individual upbringing is reasonably considered one of the most dangerous and difficult processes in life because it plays a fundamental role in forming the social personality of the individual.

Research problem and questions

During the period of the Corona pandemic, the researcher noticed some frequent positive and negative behaviors among children, which mostly attributed to the parenting style in dealing with their children. The sample of children was therefore targeted because it is the appropriate age period that shows the accurate impact of parenting style on their upbringing, especially during this critical age. Hence, this study seeks to reveal the effect of parenting style on children's behavioral problems, especially during the Corona pandemic by answering the following questions:

1. Is there an effect of the parenting style on the behavioral problems of children?
2. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems among children attributed to different parenting styles?
3. Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the effect of parenting styles on the behavioral problems among children attributed to the gender variable?

The importance of the research:

The significance of this study arises from the fact that it addresses one of the crucial issues affecting family life considering what it suffers from during the Corona pandemic. Where the significant impact of the pandemic appears on the economic, social, and living conditions in general, in addition to the lack of studies that dealt with the research variables together. This research was conducted to replenish the lack of scientific studies regarding this topic. It also stemmed its significance from its concerns with the preventive aspect, represented in understanding the nature of the reciprocal relationship between the research variables, to prepare awareness programs to educate parents on the effective methods concerning how to raise children properly.

Methods and procedures

Population and Sample

The research population consisted of all children from the age of (5- 16) years in Irbid for the year 2020, where the study sample consisted of (300) children: (150) males and (150) females, who were chosen randomly. The researcher conducted online questionnaires. Table (1) shows the distribution of the sample members according to gender variable.

Table (1): Distribution of respondents according to gender variable

variables	Category	Frequency	Percent
Gender	Male	150	50.0
	Female	150	50.0
	Total	300	100.0

Table (1) shows that the frequencies of both males and females are equal, as both recorded frequency of (150), and a ratio of (50%).

Instruments

To achieve the goals of the research, the researcher employed two instruments which are:

A. Parenting Style Scale

This measure was developed by (Riyad& Al-Moghasib, 1991), the scale comprised (70) items distributed on four domains: encouragement vs. discouragement, tolerance vs. bullying, acceptance vs. rejection, and protection vs. rejection. The measure adopted a three - rating scale (always, sometimes, rarely).

The correction criteria of the scale:In its final form, the questionnaire consisted of (70) items. The researcher utilized the 3- points Likert scale to gauge the opinions of the respondents. Their opinions were rated as following: (3 points- always); (2 points- sometimes) and (1 point- rarely). The following classification has been adopted to estimate the means as follows: (Below 1.66- low) ; (1.66-2.33 moderate) and (2.34 to 3.00) high.

B. Behavioral Problems Scale

This measure was prepared by (Al-Bassiouni, 2015), it consists of (57) items distributed into six main problems: aggressive behavior, stubbornness, shyness, excessive motor activity, lying, and stealing. A five-point scale (always / yes, often, sometimes, rarely, never / no). Table (2) shows the classification of behavioral problems including their items:

Table (2): The behavioral Problems and their items

Problems	Items	No. of Items
Aggressive behavior	2, 8, 14, 20, 26, 32, 38, 44, 50, 52, 57	11
Stubbornness	1, 7, 13, 19, 25, 31, 37, 43, 49, 56	10
Shyness	4, 10, 16, 22, 28, 34, 40, 53	8

Excessive motor activity	3, 9, 15, 21, 27, 33, 39, 45, 47, 51	10
Lying	5, 11, 17, 23, 29, 35, 41, 46, 54	9
Stealing	6, 12, 18, 24, 30, 36, 42, 48, 55	9

Correction criteria:

In its final form, the questionnaire consisted of (57) items. The researcher used the five-point Likert scale to measure the responses of the research sample rating (yes / always = 5 points), (often= 4 points), (sometimes= 3 points), (rarely= 2 points), (no / never= 1 point). Respondents must tick (✓) in front of the answer that reflects the degree of their agreement, and the following classification has been relied upon to measure the means as follows: (Below 2.33= low); (2.34-3.66= moderate) and (3.67 - 5.00= high).

Procedures

The researcher followed the following procedures in conducting the research:

1. Selecting the population and sample of the research.
2. Preparing the two study instruments and verifying the psychometric properties of the measures.
3. Distributing the questionnaires electronically via social media to the actual research sample.
4. Collecting data and processing it statistically to extract results and set recommendations.

Study variables:

- Independent variables: Parenting style, and gender (males, females)
- The dependent variable: Behavioral problems

Statistical treatment:

The current research adopted the descriptive correlational approach to study the phenomenon, understand it and explain the causative relationships precisely. To answer the research questions, the following statistical treatments were used through the Statistical Packages Program (SPSS):

- The frequencies and percentages of the variables.
- The means and standard deviations of the responses of the participants on the scale.
- Multiple Regression analysis.
- Independent-Sample (T. Test).

Results and discussion**First: Results**

This section includes the results of the research that aimed to identify the methods of parenting style from the children's viewpoint and its relationship to behavioral problems during the Corona pandemic (Covid 19). "The results were presented based on the study questions.

A. Results of the first question:

Is there an effect of the parenting style on the behavioral problems of children? To address this question, means and standard deviations were calculated for the effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems of children as shown in Table (3).

The first measure: Parenting style

Table (3): Means and standard deviations of the domains with overall scale (n = 300)

NO.	Items	Means	SD	Rank	Level
1	Encouragement vs. discouragement	1.68	0.38	3	moderate
2	Tolerance vs. bullying	1.84	0.29	1	Moderate
3	Acceptance vs. rejection	1.68	0.37	3	Moderate
4	Protection vs. neglect	1.70	0.39	2	Moderate
Total		1.72	0.33	-	Moderate

The results in Table (3) indicate that the means ranged between (1.68-1.84). "Tolerance – Bullying" came first with a mean (1.84) and a moderate level, where both "Encouragement vs. discouragement" and "Acceptance vs Rejection" ranked last with a mean (1.68) and a moderate degree. The overall mean reached (1.73) with a moderate level.

The second scale: Behavioral problems

Table (4): Means and standard deviations of the domains with the overall scale (n = 300)

NO.	Items	Means	SD	Rank	Level
1	Aggressive behavior	3.26	0.75	6	Moderate
2	Stubbornness	3.49	0.81	5	Moderate
3	Shy	3.55	0.87	3	Moderate
4	Excessive motor activity	3.50	0.82	4	Moderate
5	Lying	3.74	0.95	1	High

6	Stealing	3.56	0.79	2	Moderate
Total		3.51	0.77	-	Moderate

Table (4) shows that the means ranged between (3.26-3.74). The domain of "lying" ranked first with a mean (3.74) and a high degree, while "aggressive behavior" came in the last place with a mean (3.26) and a moderate level. The overall mean of the scale was (3.51) with a moderate degree. Accordingly, the results indicate an effect of the parenting style on the behavioral problems of children to a moderate degree.

B. Results of the second question:

Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$) for the effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems among children attributed to different parenting styles? To answer this question, Multiple Regression analysis was applied to reveal the effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems of children attributable to different parenting styles as shown in Table (5).

Table (5): Results of multiple regression analysis to reveal the effect of parenting style on children's behavioral problems attributable to different parenting styles (n = 300)

Independent variable Parenting styles	-value t	t-sig	Beta	R	R ²	value f	Sig
Encouragement vs. discouragement	4.775	0.000	0.365	0.713	0.508	76.243	0.000
Tolerance vs. bullying	1.067	0.287	0.065				
Acceptance vs. rejection	3.876	0.000	0.313				
Protection vs. neglect	1.938	0.054	0.138				

The dependent variable: Behavioral problems

Table (5) illustrates that the (f value =76.243) with statistical significance (0.000). The value of (R= 0.713), which represents the correlation coefficient of the overall model, and the value of (R² = 0.508), which represents the ratio of the influence or interpretation of all independent variables on the dependent variable, which indicates the existence of an effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems of children attributed to the differences between parenting styles.

Regarding the most significant impact of parenting style on behavioral problems was "encouragement vs. discouragement" Where the value of (t) was (4.775) with a statistically significant (0.00), followed by "acceptance vs. rejection" with the (t) value (3.876) and a statistically significant (0.00). The domain "protection vs. neglect" its (t) value was (1.938) with a statistical significance (0.054). Where the last ranked style "tolerance vs. bullying" (t=1.067) and a statistical significance (0.287).

C. Results of the third question:

Are there statistically significant differences at the level of significance ($\alpha 0.05$) in the effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems of children attributed to the gender variable? To address this question, Multiple Regression analysis was used to reveal the effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems of children attributable to the difference in the gender variable as indicated in Table (6).

Table (6): Results of multiple regression analysis to reveal the effect of parenting style on behavioral problems among children attributed to differences in gender variable (n = 300)

Gender	Independent variable Parenting style	t value	"t "sig.	Beta	R	R ²	f value	"f" sig
Male	Encouragement vs. discouragement	1.798	0.074	0.374	0.618 ^a	0.382	22.381	0.00
	Tolerance vs. bullying	0.113	0.911	0.023				
	Acceptance vs. rejection	3.791	0.000	0.999				
	Protection vs. neglect	0.662	0.509	0.142				
Female	Encouragement vs. discouragement	4.957	.000	1.182	0.737 ^b	.543	43.078	0.00
	Tolerance vs. bullying	1.176	0.242	0.306				
	Acceptance vs. rejection	1.262	0.209	0.302				
	Protection vs. neglect	1.057	0.292	0.209				

The dependent variable: Behavioral problems

Regarding the male variable Table (6) illustrates that the value of (f= 22,381), with statistical significance (0.000). The value of (R= 0.618), which represents the correlation coefficient of the overall modal, and the value

of ($R^2 = 0.382$), which represents the ratio of the influence or interpretation of all independent variables on the dependent variable, which indicates an effect of parenting style on behavioral problems of male children.

As illustrated in Table (6), the most influential parenting style affecting the occurrence of behavioral problems among males is "acceptance vs. rejection"; Where the value of ($t = 3.791$) and with statistical significance (0.00), followed by "encouragement vs. discouragement", with the value of ($t = 1.798$), with statistically significant (0.074); Where the area of "protection vs. neglect," came with the value of ($t = 0.662$) and a statistical significance (0.509). The last ranked area is "tolerance versus bullying", which came with the value of ($t = 0.113$) and with a statistical significance (0.911).

Concerning the most prominent parenting style that has an impact on the behavioral problems of females is the style of "encouragement vs. discouragement, where the value of ($t = 4.957$) and a statistically significant (0.00), followed by "acceptance vs. rejection," where the value of ($t = 1.262$) and a statistical significance (0.209), "tolerance vs. bullying" style ($t = 1.176$) and a statistical significance (0.242). The last influential style was "protection vs. negligence", where the value of ($t = 1.057$) and a statistical significance (0.292). Consequently, there are differences between males and females in the effect of parenting styles on behavioral problems, and the most prominent among males was the field of "acceptance vs. rejection", while the most prominent for females was the field of "encouragement vs. discouragement." Generally, the effect of parenting styles on behavioral problems among females is higher than that of males. The differences between males and females were also revealed in the domains of behavioral problems as shown in Table (7).

Table (7): Independent - Sample T-Test results to identify differences among children's behavioral problems attributable to the gender variable.

Domains	Gender	N	Means	SD	Value"t"	Sig
Aggressive behavior	Male	150	3.10	0.67	-3.763	0.000
	Female	150	3.42	0.79		
Stubbornness	Male	150	3.25	0.69	-5.325	0.000
	Female	150	3.73	0.84		
Shyness	Male	150	3.25	0.81	-6.298	0.000
	Female	150	3.85	0.83		
Excessive motor activity	Male	150	3.26	0.68	-5.283	0.000
	Female	150	3.74	0.88		
Lying	Male	150	3.48	0.86	-4.803	0.000
	Female	150	3.99	0.97		
Stealing	Male	150	3.36	0.72	-4.717	0.000
	Female	150	3.77	0.79		
Total	Male	150	3.28	0.67	-5.393	0.000
	Female	150	3.74	0.79		

Table (7) shows that the most prominent behavioral problems for males are the problem of lying with a mean of (3.48), followed by the problem of stealing with a mean of (3.36), and finally the problem of aggressive behavior with a mean of (3.10). As for females, the most prominent behavioral problem is the problem of lying with a mean of (3.99), followed by the problem of shyness with a mean of (3.85), and the last ranked problem is the aggressive behavior with a mean of (3.42).

Discussion of results

According to the abovementioned results, we found that:

- There is an effect of the parenting style on the behavioral problems of children to a moderate level. The researcher attributes this result to the importance of the role of the family and parents in raising a mentally, socially, and behaviorally healthy generation, especially considering the Corona pandemic, and the psychological pressures that children are exposed to because of being deprived of their normal lives, going out of the house, and playing with peers. Where the parenting style adopted by the family plays a key role in influencing the child's behavior during this period, either in terms of directing the child to appropriate behavior using methods of protection, encouragement, acceptance, and tolerance or by imposing pressures which, as a result, will lead to improper behavior through methods of rejection, neglect, discouraging.

Al-Sayed et al. (1998) consider upbringing as the source of customs, traditions, norms, and general rules of conduct. According to (Al-Zaliti, 2008) the process of upbringing takes place through parents adopting a set of methods in raising their children, and how to deal with them in different situations and issues they face, considering that parents are a source of authority, knowledge, and the idealism. Misbah (2003) sees that psychological, financial, and social pressures and the pressures resulting from the environment and surrounding circumstances and health pressures such as diseases and epidemics have a crucial impact on the family system and its relationships and the upbringing of its children. Ahmed (2000) believes that individuals who grow up in an

unstable family atmosphere suffer from emotional, behavioral, and social problems. Aboobaker et al study (2019) aimed to identify the predictors of emotional and behavioral problems among Indian adolescents on a group of (81) parents of adolescents who are among the age group (10 to 18) years from the National Institute of Mental Health and Neurosciences in India, they assured that the age of Adolescence, parenting involvement, parents age, and parental practices are important predictors of emotional and behavioral problems. The study demonstrated the role of abnormal psychosocial environments and negative parenting practices as risk factors for emotional and behavioral problems among adolescents.

- There is an effect of parenting style on the behavioral problems of children attributed to the different methods of parenting styles; The most influential style on behavioral problems was the encouragement vs. discouragement, while the least influential style the tolerance vs. bullying style. The researcher attributes this to the fact that encouragement increases the child's self-confidence, increases self-conception, independence, and self-reliance, and thus directs the child to the right behavior. While discouragement leads to undermining self-confidence, frustration, and a tendency to abnormal behavior. Al-Muhaidin and Al-Nawaisa (2009) yield that behavioral problems lead to difficulty of compatibility with others, impede psychological and social development, and weaken self-confidence. In the same regard, Pryanka (2013) notes that an un-peaceful family upbringing leads to feelings of depression, despair, introversion, sadness, and the desire to rebel against sources of authority in the family, school, and society. Furthermore, Misbah (2003) points out that the family environment contributes to the upbringing process through social relations and family interactions, which differ from one family to another according to the nature of the social and economic statuses and according to the composition of the family. For a family that is dominated by an atmosphere of stability and harmony, the relationship of its members is based on love, respect, cooperation, and understanding, unlike the family where hostility and turmoil prevail among its members. The study of (Balamri, 2016) indicates that the correct methods of parenting style are those that are based on encouragement, motivation, reward, cooperation, solidarity, and tolerance, which would reduce the severity of aggression, violence, and abnormal behaviors among children.

- There are differences between males and females in the impact of parenting styles on behavioral problems, as it has a higher impact in favor of females. Where the most prominent parenting style among males was the field of "acceptance vs. rejection", while the most prominent for females was the field of "encouragement vs. discouragement." The researcher attributes this to the fact that children in childhood and during the Corona period and the absence of normal life need encouragement, acceptance, and closer attachment to their parents more to cover the void that their distance from peers, play, and the school atmosphere creates. The results of the study of (Ahmed A., 2005), which aimed to identify the methods of parenting styles and their relationship to school behavioral and psychological problems for adolescents on a sample of (440) male and female students, showed that there is a relationship between parenting styles and behavioral and psychological problems of adolescent students and that the most predictive variables of these problems are discouragement, neglect, rejection, and bullying.

- The most prominent behavioral problem for males and females was the problem of lying, and the least prominent was the problem of aggressive behavior. The researcher attributes this to the child's resorting to lying to defend himself and his private property, which has become available to everyone due to the new life conditions that the Corona pandemic has created, and he also resorts to lying to get rid of the tasks assigned to him. As for the aggressive behavior, it was less prominent because this problem is limited to dealing with family members and the permanent presence of the parents, which limits the increase of this problem compared to it when children depart the house and interact with peers.

Regarding lying, (Ghazi, 1999) believes that lying is more common than other behaviors, not because children like to lie, rather, because they were raised in family educational conditions that reinforced that behavior. Generally speaking, although children in any society are born equipped with physical and psychological characteristics and the ability to acquire moral qualities, family environmental, education and parenting styles determine the characteristics of a child's behavior.

With respect to aggressive behavior, (Al-Hamidi, 2004) pointed out in his study, which aimed to identify the relationship between aggressive behavior and methods of parenting styles among a sample of middle school students in the State of Qatar, that the aggressive behavior among students who experienced negative parental practices increased, unlike what was mentioned in the current research. A study conducted by (Fite et al, 2008), which aimed to identify the relationship between parental pressure and aggressive behavior among children, on a sample of (212) children, showed a high degree of aggressive behavior among children who suffer from parental pressure.

Conclusion

Through our research, we concluded that the impact of family communication on the social upbringing of children makes a significant contribution to shaping the personality of their children and to developing the spirit of belonging to their societies. In this study, we address some of the parenting styles such as encouragement,

tolerance, acceptance, and protection within the family that would lead to a healthy and normal social upbringing for children, and parents' distancing from the style of bullying, neglect, rejection, and other negative methods that accrue to the child's psyche negatively over time. It is known that childhood and adolescence are critical stages because the child moves to a new stage in which he is easily subject to change and deviance, mainly if his personality is not strong and his upbringing is not sound. Communication and interaction are essential social processes in a person's life, through which he understands all the components of his environment including individuals who live around him as no human or social organization can survive without it. Social communication is the foundation of social systems and the pillar of relationships that arise between individuals, regardless of their goals or to the type of community group they belong to. Undoubtedly, the most prominent organization in which these relationships begin is the family which is considered the first social cornerstone.

Recommendations

- Considering the results of the current research, the researcher recommends the following:
- Avoiding the use of inappropriate methods in dealing with the child by the parents.
- Fostering dialogue between parents and children and encourage them to express their thoughts and opinions freely with the necessity of providing constant guidance.
- Ensuring to provide equal upbringing among their children and raising them soundly and solid foundations.
- Promoting the prevalence of an atmosphere of tranquility and a sense of success, enhance self-confidence, and provide support and encouragement to children.
- Making time for children, paying attention to their problems, listening to them, and assisting them in solving their problems.
- Enhancing parental containment to their children's behavior.
- Converging efforts between the various social institutions, starting from the family to the school and the role of the media.
- Raising awareness through the media and various family welfare organizations, on the use of proper parenting styles.

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